

BODC Data Submission: designing a new app

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About this work

The BOOST EDS project, [funded by UKRI and supported by DSIT](#), aimed to pilot a range of measures to address issues of data findability, traceability, accessibility and interoperability, to improve data sharing and access across disciplines. Conducted from late 2023 to March 2025, the project consisted of five work packages, with one work package dedicated to user centred approaches in the context of environmental data services. The work was undertaken by members of the NERC Environmental Data Service (EDS).

This is a summary report to provide supporting information to the overarching report - User centred approaches for environmental data services: embedding co-creation and collaboration (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115280>)

Summary

The submission of data workflow to data centres has been overlooked for years. The British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC) decided to look at our submission system and redesign it in a user-friendly way to encourage more frequent submissions with more complete metadata. By providing a guided workflow, BODC can ensure that submissions are transparent, more complete, and more consistent. This in turn should make the process easier for data originators, and the archiving and ingestion of the data quicker for data managers.

Rationale for the work

At BODC, submissions were all manual and based on emails or file transfer systems without an easy and straightforward way to capture essential metadata. This then meant data submitters had to know exactly who to email to submit their data to, and do their best at gathering the correct metadata in a workable format. Data managers then had to go through all the data files and metadata files submitted to ensure they had enough information to process the data, and then archive the files straight away as there was no secure holding stage, which put a very high load on data managers.

As a result of ad hoc email submissions, there was also a wide variety of file formats being submitted. This makes it even more difficult for data managers to check data in a consistent way and hinders the onward ingestion of the data into our database.

Creating a self-service web application for data submission provides users with a clear and guided process for capturing correct metadata, helping them to understand what is needed up-front while also reducing manual intervention from data managers.

Methodology

The data submission app was created using Scrum methods to find solutions to issues by building a tool that can be improved over time with consistent feedback from users. It started with a series of in-person workshops made up of BODC data managers to find pain points in the submission process. Data managers have a wealth of knowledge of common issues they run into during the submission process. They often get feedback on submissions through liaising with data originators upon submissions, so they are a hugely valuable resource for where to start to begin to ease the process. Once these points were captured, they were prioritised in order of what would provide the biggest impact to data managers.

When the app was in a state where it could capture the essential metadata required for data publication in a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), and after extensive internal use by BODC data managers, BODC did a soft launch of the app to trusted scientists who provide a lot of submissions to BODC within the National Oceanography Centre (NOC) where BODC is hosted. Alongside the submissions, a feedback form was sent out for the originators to fill in and help identify areas of improvement. Using Scrum, this feedback was acted on and the app was improved for external users.

After a successful soft launch and some more internal testing, the app was fully launched as BODC's main submission route for all delayed mode data, it allows submitters to receive DOIs for their data with a much quicker turnaround than before in a more transparent way.

Lessons learnt

It would be useful to have more consistent feedback from our external data submitters as they go through the submission process. There are barriers that prevent us from doing this, so we need a consistent approach to ensure we are not breaching any confidentiality. The use of Scrum has been extremely beneficial in terms of taking direct feedback and building up a basic app to a fully functional system.

An initial version of the application was built based on the core requirements, but with a small focus on the user experience, which had an internal release. Unfortunately, there were a number of issues around the technical implementation and architecture that made it clear that a second version would be required. This gave us a valuable opportunity to gather feedback on version 1 and use it to ensure that the rebuild could have a strong focus on the user experience and meet their needs first and foremost.

This process has emphasised the importance of integrating user feedback. Going forward we are looking at ways to gather feedback from a range of users, such as integrating feedback surveys into the application's user journey.

Opportunities and future recommendations

It would be useful to have clear guidelines on how the Environmental Data Services (EDS) data centres can put out surveys for their users and utilise feedback. Building the app also highlights how well Scrum can work when it's followed properly, particularly with the use of a dedicated Product Owner working in close partnership with a Technical Lead. The app has been built in a way that can be integrated into other data centre's back ends to potentially move towards having one single interface for all data submissions into the EDS, which would make submissions even easier for end users, particularly if they work on cross-discipline projects.

BODC can also use the basis of the app to facilitate the onward ingestion of data that is submitted via the app. By capturing the metadata in a central point, the metadata can be pushed onwards and into the systems used for full ingestion requiring much less load on data managers.